

Theoretical studies on the charge transfer complexes of aromatic hydrocarbons with chloranil^ψ

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Molecular orbital and molecular mechanics calculation have been done to obtain informations about some general physico-chemical proportion of charge transfer complexes of benzene, naphthalene and anthracene with chloranil. The semi-empirical quantum chemical programme MOPAC and the AMI^{1,2} method has been used.

Molecular charge-transfer complexes have been studied widely and numerous experimental data are available. Elaborate molecular calculations on the complexes has so far not been reported. *Ab initio* calculations on these large molecular complexes are rather impossible even with advanced computers of today. Hence semi-empirical molecular orbital calculations are carried out with AMI of Dewar for calculating the optimized geometric parameters, dipole moment, heat of formation and nuclear quadrupole resonance parameters.

Computational details :

The semi-empirical molecular orbital calculations were done on Super 32 Computer in the Variable Energy Cyclotron Center at Kolkata, India. The molecular complexes were made with models placing chloranil at the Van der Waals distance of 3.2 Å and parallel to the hydrocarbons. The center of chloranil was in line with the center of the corresponding hydrocarbons. The energy minimization was continued until the energies remained constant after several iteration.

Nuclear quadrupole resonance shift was calculated by the method due to Kaplansky and Whitehead³ later on followed by Santhanam and Sobhanadri⁴. According to them if (a) the principal axis of the effective field gradient, efg, at a nucleus are known and if (b) the population matrix for the wave functions of the electrons at the nucleus can be related to the principal axes of the efg and if (c) the principal axis of the efg are selected so that efg matrix is diagonal, then the population matrix will also be diagonal, so that diagonal population matrix elements are

directly related to the e^2Qq/h . Then the efg matrix in its simplest diagonal form is related to the population matrix, which is also in the diagonal form in the following way :

$$q_{zz} = [P_{zz} - 1/2(P_{xx} + P_{yy})] Q_{zz}^{PZ}$$

Results and discussion

Tables 1 and 2 contain structural data like bond lengths, bond angles and twist angles of the complexes I, II and III. Table 3 contains the heats of formation, dipole moments, electronic energies and ionisation potentials of the complexes. Table 4 contains the NQR coupling constants, NQR shift and ionization potentials of the hydrocarbons. Table 5 contains the structural formulas of the complexes.

The Table 1 shows that the Van der Waals distances (3.2 Å) as given in the input data are not maintained in complexes I and II (value is nearly 5 Å), and also the stacking of chloranil on the hydrocarbons are not parallel but a bit slanting. For the complex III however the Van der Waals distances (3.2 Å) is exactly maintained and the stacking is exactly parallel. In all the three complexes the hexagon of chloranil is uniformly flattened. Accordingly the bond angles and dihedral angles are changed as shown in Table 2.

Heats of formation data shows complex III to be more stable than complexes I and II. This is corroborated experimentally in this laboratory as anthracene-chloranil complex crystals had been isolated and studied by oscillating photography whereas crystals I and II suffer mas-

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Table 1. Calculated bond lengths (Å) for the complexes

Bond	Bond length (Å)	Bond	Bond length (Å)
Benzene-chloranil complex			
1-2	1.394	20-27	1.690
2-3	1.396	21-28	1.232
3-4	1.393	22-29	1.691
4-5	1.394	23-30	1.690
5-6	1.395	19-8	5.075
1-6	1.396	20-7	5.325
13-14	1.354	23-2	4.963
14-15	1.487	22-3	4.752
15-16	1.487	24-18	4.685
16-17	1.352	21-5	4.807
17-18	1.486	Anthracene-chloranil complex	
18-13	1.490	1-2	1.400
13-20	1.691	2-3	1.433
14-21	1.687	3-4	1.367
15-22	1.233	4-5	1.428
16-23	1.687	5-6	1.368
17-24	1.692	6-7	1.431
18-19	1.231	7-8	1.400
13-2	4.551	8-9	1.400
14-3	4.516	9-10	1.430
17-6	4.744	10-11	1.367
16-5	4.719	11-12	1.425
18-1	4.637	12-13	1.368
15-4	4.595	13-14	1.429
Naphthalene-chloranil complex			
1-2	1.374	1-14	1.399
2-3	1.416	9-14	1.400
3-4	1.373	2-7	1.400
4-5	1.421	25-26	1.353
5-6	1.422	26-27	1.487
6-7	1.372	27-28	1.488
7-8	1.420	28-29	1.350
8-9	1.372	29-30	1.488
9-18	1.422	25-30	1.486
1-18	1.420	30-31	1.232
5-18	1.418	25-32	1.690
19-20	1.353	26-33	1.689
20-21	1.487	27-34	1.232
21-22	1.487	28-35	1.692
22-23	1.352	29-36	1.691
23-24	1.487	30-1	3.200
24-25	1.231	25-14	3.200
19-26	1.690	26-9	3.200
		27-8	3.200
		28-7	3.200
		29-2	3.200

Table-1 (contd.)

Table 2. Calculated bond angles and twist angles in degrees for the complexes

(I) Benzene-chloranil complex			
Atom no.	Bond angle	Atom no.	Twist angle
3-2-1	120.73	-	-
4-3-2	119.14	4-3-2-1	-1.78
5-4-3	120.54	5-4-3-2	+0.37
6-5-4	120.00	6-5-4-3	+1.42
8-1-6	120.12	8-1-6-5	-179.26
10-3-2	120.47	10-3-2-1	+178.83
y-5-4	54.48	y-5-4-3	-14.09
x-y-5	92.87	x-y-5-6	+82.87
13-x-y	103.87	13-x-y-1	+65.60
14-13-x	90.96	14-13-x-y	+72.72
15-14-13	121.36	15-14-13-x	+23.94
16-15-14	116.81	16-15-14-13	0.006
18-17-16	122.60	18-17-16-15	-0.75
20-13-18	116.25	20-13-18-17	177.65
22-15-14	121.57	22-15-14-13	179.84
24-17-16	121.12	24-17-16-15	179.51
(II) Naphthalene-chloranil complex			
3-2-1	120.22	-	-
4-3-2	120.60	4-3-2-1	+0.06
5-4-3	120.25	5-4-3-2	-0.16
6-5-4	121.97	6-5-4-3	179.93
7-6-5	121.15	7-6-5-4	-179.90
8-7-6	120.14	8-7-6-5	+0.16
9-8-7	119.72	9-8-7-6	+0.26
10-9-8	120.54	10-9-8-7	179.66
12-7-8	119.07	12-7-8-11	+0.10
14-4-5	118.78	14-4-5-6	+0.07
16-2-3	119.20	16-2-3-15	+0.05
18-9-8	121.34	18-9-8-7	-0.51
Y-18-1	113.55	Y-18-1-2	21.87
X-Y-18	97.61	X-Y-18-9	-76.97
19-X-Y	104.15	19-X-Y-18	125.86
20-19-X	74.14	20-19-X-Y	81.27
21-20-19	122.22	21-20-19-X	22.32
23-22-21	122.54	23-22-21-20	-0.37
25-24-23	122.24	25-24-23-22	179.59
27-20-19	121.33	27-20-19-26	+0.31
29-22-21	116.29	29-22-21-28	-0.04
(III) Anthracene-chloranil complex			
3-2-1	121.94	-	-
4-3-2	120.56	4-3-2-1	-178.59
5-4-3	120.62	5-4-3-2	-1.58
6-5-4	120.50	6-5-4-3	+0.67

Table-2 (contd.)

7-6-5	120.35	7-6-5-4	+0.79
8-7-6	120.55	8-7-6-5	177.95
9-8-7	119.83	9-8-7-6	-179.46
10-9-8	120.37	10-9-8-7	-179.88
11-10-9	120.55	11-10-9-8	+178.71
12-11-10	120.45	12-11-10-9	+0.26
13-12-11	120.24	13-12-11-10	+0.06
14-13-12	120.98	14-13-12-11	-0.11
15-1-2	119.60	15-1-14-13	-0.96
17-4-3	120.89	17-4-3-16	-0.10
19-6-7	121.35	19-6-5-18	+0.16
21-10-9	118.29	21-10-9-8	-1.40
23-12-11	119.19	23-12-11-22	+0.28
24-13-12	120.9	24-13-12-23	-0.35
Y-1-2	68.78	Y-1-2-7	+23.68
X-Y-1	104.25	X-Y-1-2	87.60
25-X-Y	98.97	25-X-Y-1	67.30
26-25-X	60.10	26-25-X-Y	88.35
27-26-25	120.11	27-26-25-X	+18.24
29-28-27	122.40	29-28-27-26	+0.13
31-30-29	122.12	31-30-29-28	-179.50
33-26-25	121.43	33-26-25-30	179.93
35-28-27	116.21	35-28-27-26	+179.70

for chloroprene⁴. The table is given for ready reference. Further the values show a downward trend contrary to experimental values. Douglass^{8,9} believed that since ionic character of the halogen carbon depends on the electron density at the carbon the electronic transfer from donor to the chloranil would result in a decrease of the chlorine resonant frequency in the complex relative to pure chlorine and such was the case here. Theoretical calculation was done only on single charge-transfer molecules, made up of one chloranil and one hydrocarbon whereas in the experimental field there are always some chance of each chlorine being influenced by other polynuclear hydrocarbons from the neighbouring crystal sites. However these extraneous effects had not been calculated so far our knowledge goes. The degree of charge-transfer is related directly to the ionization potential of the donor according

Fig. 1

sive damage under X-ray radiation and X-ray photography could not be taken⁵. Dipole moment data shows good correlation with experimental values obtained in this laboratory^{6,7}.

The NQR frequencies of these complexes as reported in Table 4 shows a wide difference from experimentally reported values. The same was true for the reported value

Table 3. Calculated heats of formation, dipole moment, electronic energy and ionisation potential of charge transfer complexes

Complex	Hf (kcal/mol)	Dipole moment		Electronic energy (eV)	Ionisation potential (eV)
		Calcd. (Debye)	Expt. (Debye)		
Benzene-chloranil	-17.007	0.017	-	-1957.247	9.766
Naphthalene-chloranil	+1.2716	0.110	0.060	-25845.042	8.799
Anthracene-chloranil	+23.670	0.121	0.135	-32634.179	8.179

Table 4. Nuclear quadrupole coupling constants in MHz

	Theoretical Calcd. by AMI method	Experimental			
Chloranil	101.181	101.219	101.302	101.158	37.50
Benz-chloranil	100.899	101.260	101.295	100.892	37.67
Naph-chloranil	100.902	100.965	100.985	100.845	37.75
Anth-chloranil	100.973	101.003	101.050	100.900	38.26

Chloroprene (4)	NQR of chloroprene		Experimental
	83.93 (CNDO)	Theoretical 90.38 (AMI)	
	NQR shift (MHz) of molecular complexes with respect to chloranil and ionization potentials (eV) of the polynuclear hydrocarbons		
	NQR shift (MHz)	I (in eV)	
Benz-chloranil	0.282	8.60	
Naph-chloranil	0.279	8.30	
Anth-chloranil	0.208	7.74	

Table 5. Structural formulas of the charge transfer complexes

(I) Benzene-chloranil complex

(II) Naphthalene-chloranil complex

(III) Anthracene-chloranil complex

Dotted line indicates the perpendicular distance between the centres of chloranil and corresponding hydrocarbon (3.2 Å).

to Mulliken. Hence we can expect linear relationship between the NQR frequency shift and ionization potential of the donors. As is observed there is a linear relationship (Fig. 1) between the NQR frequency shift and the ionization potential of the donors.

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